

Appraisal of the Regulatory and Institutional Framework for Solid Waste Management in Nigeria

*Roseline O. Moses-Oke, PhD,
Associate Professor of Law,
Western Delta University,
Oghara, Delta State, Nigeria.
Email: moses-oke@wdu.edu.ng*

Abstract:

Waste management in Nigeria has become a growing problem due to the resultant effect of high waste generation, urbanization, population increase, poor infrastructure, inadequate waste collection and disposal. This occasioned environmental degradation, pollution, health hazards and environmental damage. The legal and institutional provisions for waste management, which is divided among federal, State, and local governments, with overlapping obligations have not been properly enforced to resolve the situation. This study examined Nigeria's legal and institutional framework for solid wastes management. The study employed the doctrinal approach, making use of both primary and secondary sources of information. The primary sources encompass the actual legal documents and authoritative materials that form the foundation of the legal framework. Secondary sources utilized include journals articles, books, reports and Internet materials. Information obtained from these sources were subjected to content analysis and critically evaluated for relevance and reliability. This study revealed that Nigeria has passed a number of regulations to control solid waste, but the problems with the various trash dump sites are caused by the laxity in the implementation of these regulations. Findings also showed that waste management in Nigeria is still quite problematic with issues ranging from inefficient waste collection methods to insufficient infrastructure. In conclusion, to properly address the issue, more financing and investment, education and awareness initiatives, in addition with sustainable waste management techniques are required.

Keywords: Solid wastes, waste management, environment, laws, institutions, pollution, Nigeria.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Waste management is a crucial issue that has impacts on the environment, public health, and sustainable development of countries all over the world.¹ It is critical for reducing environmental pollution, protecting human health, and promoting resource efficiency.² The waste management problem in Nigeria is particularly acute, with the country generating an estimated 20 million tons of solid waste annually.³ This waste is often disposed of in an indiscriminate manner, which results in environmental and health challenges. Waste management has emerged as a critical issue in Nigeria, a country undergoing a fast population increase and urbanisation. Inadequate infrastructure, weak policies, and limited resources contribute to the spread of waste and the accompanying problems.⁴

The legal and institutional framework for waste management is divided among federal, State, and local governments, with overlapping obligations and insufficient resources.⁵ Lagos States has implemented waste management laws and regulations to address the issue. These laws create legal frameworks for waste management practices while imposing consequences for non-compliance. Despite these efforts, waste management in Nigeria continues to be a severe burden, with issues ranging from insufficient infrastructure to improper waste collection practices. To effectively solve the problem, sustainable waste management practices, education, awareness initiatives, and more funding and investment are required.⁶

Careless garbage disposal has grown to be a serious problem for both people and the environment, mostly in industrial and municipal regions. For those living in the neighborhoods surrounding the disposal sites, it has resulted in several health issues. Climate change, flooding, air, water, and soil pollution, and the promotion of the growth of bacteria and viruses that cause infectious diseases have all been connected to poor

¹ The World Bank, 'What a Waste 2.0: A Global Snapshot of Solid Waste Management to 2050' (2020), Accessed at <<https://www.worldbank.org/en/news/immersive-story/2018/09/20/what-a-waste-an-updated-look-into-the-future-of-solid-waste-management>> accessed 30/01/2025.

² United Nations Environment Programme, 'Global Waste Management Outlook' (2018) Accessed at <www.unep.org/resources/global-waste-management-outlook-2018> accessed 07/02/2025.

³ C. Nwifo, 'The legal framework for waste management in Nigeria' (2020) 32(2) *Journal of Environmental Law*, 233-252.

⁴ A. Awasthi and S. Mukherjee, 'Waste Management in Nigeria: Challenges and opportunities' (2019) 37(1) *Waste Management & Research*, 1-11.

⁵ O.A Ogunsanwo and O. Afolabi, 'Waste Management in Nigeria: A review of the legal and institutional framework' (2019) 11(2) *Journal of Environmental Management*, 242.

⁶ A. Awasthi and S. Mukherjee, 'Waste Management in Nigeria: Challenges and opportunities' (2019) 37(1) *Waste Management & Research*, 1-11.

waste management and incorrect disposal.⁷ The majority of the local population is ignorant of the negative consequences of trash disposal, aside from the unpleasant smells that permeate the messy area.⁸

It is crucial for nations to put policies, frameworks, and strategies in place to reduce these effects by implementing proper disposal management, given the increase in activities that result in the accumulation of waste that is already improperly disposed of and mismanaged and the ensuing environmental degradation. According to researchers, these frameworks and tactics are based on institutional and legal laws that limit and regulate how trash is managed and what people can do with it.⁹ The federal, state, and local governments in Nigeria have different legal frameworks for garbage management.

These laws seek to clarify the duties and obligations of many stakeholders, create a framework for efficient waste management, and encourage environmentally friendly waste management techniques.¹⁰ The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act of 2007 is one of the waste management-related laws passed by the federal government. This law creates the NESREA, which oversees Nigeria's environmental laws and standards.¹¹ Waste management is a responsibility of the state governments as well. The NESREA Act and other waste management-related laws are enforced by the environmental protection agency of each state. Within their borders, municipal administrations are in charge of gathering and getting rid of waste.¹²

The laws, rules, and policies that now control waste management methods are examined in this study. It aims to determine the legal frameworks' advantages and disadvantages, evaluate how well they handle waste management issues, and make suggestions for improving waste management procedures.

2. OVERVIEW OF SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIA

Nigeria is among the most populous nations in the world and the most populous in Africa. There are 37 capital cities and a large number of urban and semi-urban areas in Nigeria,

⁷ D. Omang and others, 'Public health implication of solid waste generated by households in Bekwarra Local Government area' (2021) 56(11) *Journal of Environmental Science and Health, Part A: Toxic/Hazardous Substances and Environmental Engineering*, 1467-1476.

⁸ X. Yan and F.P Sankoh and Q. Tran, 'Environmental and Health Impact of solid waste disposal in developing cities' (2013) *A Canville Brook Dumpsite case study Freetown, Sierra Leone J Environ Protection* 4: 665-670.

⁹ S. Rajendran and others, 'Influential aspects in waste management practices' (2019) *Waste Management* 84, 67-76.

¹⁰ D. Akande 'The Multifaceted Waste Management Issues in Nigeria: Lagos State as a Case Study' (2018) *SSRN Electronic Journal*. doi: 10.2139/ssrn.3235345

¹¹ National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Act (2007).

¹² Federal Ministry of Environment, 'Nigeria: National Policy on Waste Management' (2020).

which consists of 36 States and a Federal Capital Territory. The massive volumes of garbage produced every day by human and industrial activity are problematic because there are either insufficient or no procedures in place to deal with the resulting obligation for waste disposal.¹³

Many Nigerian states have had difficulty managing their waste, and there are mountains of trash in many places, which has a negative impact on the quality of life and the environment. Additionally, this jeopardises invisible environmental elements like clean air and groundwater supplies. In many regions of the nation, private waste management firms handle all or part of the garbage disposal for businesses and residential residences.¹⁴ The majority of the waste management system is still antiquated, with dumpsites still being used extensively and recycling receiving little to no attention.¹⁵ This clearly indicates that Nigeria's waste management system is in general experiencing severe failures. Sorting, storing, collecting, transporting, processing, recovering resources, recycling, and disposing of waste are all included in municipal waste management.¹⁶

There are several different ways to manage and dispose of waste in Nigeria. Nigeria has a lot of regulations, but they have not helped the country achieve excellence in garbage management and disposal. Aside from the meager efforts made by families to clean up their immediate surroundings and the fact that almost all states have regulations that set aside at least one day of the month for "general clean-up,"¹⁷ and have laws that create offences for non-compliance with these regulations, waste disposal and management are still indiscriminate in many places and cities, with wastes dumped on roadsides, in drainage channels, and gully erosion sites.

¹³O.S Amuda, S.A. Adebisi, L.A. Jimoda & A.O. Alade, 'Challenges and possible panacea to the municipal solid wastes management in Nigeria' (2014) 6(2) *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*, 67-76; B.O Uwadiogwu and K.E Chukwu, 'Strategies for effective urban solid waste management in Nigeria' (2013) 9(8) *European Scientific Journal*, 296-307.

¹⁴B.O Uwadiogwu and K.E Chukwu, 'Strategies for effective urban solid waste management in Nigeria' (2013) 9(8) *European Scientific Journal*, 298-307.

¹⁵A.J Oloruntade et al. 'Municipal solid waste collection and management strategies in Akure, south-western Nigeria' (2013) 11(1) *Caspian Journal of Environmental Science*, 5-16.

¹⁶B. Abila and J. Kantola, 'Municipal solid waste management problems in Nigeria: Evolving knowledge management solutions' (2013) 7(6) *International Journal of Environmental, Earth Science, and Engineering*, 12-21.

¹⁷A.J Oloruntade et al. 'Municipal solid waste collection and management strategies in Akure, south-western Nigeria' (2013) 11(1) *Caspian Journal of Environmental Science*, 5-16.

States that have enabling laws to regulate waste management and, in certain situations, recycling operations¹⁸ also have a variety of waste management organizations.¹⁹ For example, Ondo State has two organizations: the Ondo State Integrated Wastes Recycling and Treatment Project (OSIWRTP), which deals with recycling, and the Ondo State Waste Management Agency (OSWMA), which addresses the problem of disposing of municipal waste. The Kano State Environmental Protection Agency (KEPA) is another trash management organization in Kano State. Kano's garbage collection, transportation, and disposal are handled by KEPA. Additionally, KEPA encourages citizens to recycle their waste through its recycling program.²⁰ There are other deplorable wastes dumpsite in Olusosun landfill in Lagos, Gosa landfill in Abuja, and others in Kano.

Numerous private companies and waste collectors have made substantial contributions to the improvement of waste management in Nigeria,²¹ and their efforts should not be disregarded. Waste recycling is also done by waste collectors and private companies.

Nonetheless, Nigerian municipalities continue to dispose of their trash primarily through open dumping, open burning, incineration, uncontrolled landfills, composting, and dumping into drain channels, streams, and rivers. Thus, in many Nigerian cities and towns, municipal garbage management has emerged as the most urgent problem.²² The scale of the problem is captured in figure 1 below. The oldest known issue is that solid waste accumulates because waste collection²³ and evacuation frequently fall behind waste generation.²⁴ Other contemporary problems include funding,²⁵ government agencies' unacceptable waste disposal practices,²⁶ and Nigeria's general underinvestment in modern waste management technologies like recycling facilities or plants.

¹⁸ For example, 'The Lagos State Waste Management Authority website' < www.lawma.gov.ng > Accessed 10/03/2025

¹⁹ B. Abila and J. Kantola, 'Municipal solid waste management problems in Nigeria: Evolving knowledge management solutions' (2013) 7(6) *International Journal of Environmental, Earth Science, and Engineering*, 13-21.

²⁰ Environmental Law Research Institute, 'Compilation of Institutions & Waste Management Regulations in Nigeria' (8 March 2023) < https://www.elri-ng.org/newsandrelease2_waste.html > accessed 30 January 2025.

²¹ O.O Adebola, 'The roles of the informal private sector in integrated solid waste management in achieving Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) in Lagos, Nigeria' (In Solid Waste, Health & Millennium Development Goals, CWG-WASH Workshop, Kolkata 2006)

²² A.J Oloruntade et al. 'Municipal solid waste collection and management strategies in Akure, south-western Nigeria' (2013) 11(1) *Caspian Journal of Environmental Science*, 1-16.

²³ See <https://ehcon.gov.ng/solid-waste-collection-services-providers/> Accessed 21/05/2025

²⁴ O.S Amuda et al. 'Challenges and possible panacea to the municipal solid wastes management in Nigeria' (2014) 6(2) *Journal of Sustainable Development Studies*, 67-76; B.O Uwadiogwu and K.E Chukwu, 'Strategies for effective urban solid waste management in Nigeria' (2013) 9(8) *European Scientific Journal*, 296-307.

²⁵ V.I Ogu, 'Private sector participation and municipal waste management in Benin City, Nigeria' (2000) 12(2) *Journal of Environment and Urbanization*, 103-117.

²⁶ National Agency For Food, Drug Administration And Control, 'NAFDAC destroys expired drugs in specialist hospital' < www.nanngronline.com/section/general/nafdac-destorys-expired-drugs-in-specialist-hospital > accessed 10 March 2025.

Figure 1: Olusosun Landfill, Lagos, Nigeria.

Source: Temitope Agbotoba, "Lagos Landfills: Mountains of Trash Pose Threats to Humans, Environment". The Premium Times, 3rd February 2024. Available at <https://www.premiumtimesng.com/regional/ssouth-west/664339-lagos-landfills-mountains-of-trash-pose-threat-to-humans-environment.html?tztc=1> accessed on 13th May 2025.

3. SOLID WASTE MANAGEMENT IN NIGERIA VIA THE LEGAL INSTRUMENT

Nigeria's enormous population and lack of adequate mechanisms to handle the increasing amount of waste generated every day make waste management a significant concern. An overview of waste management in Nigeria is given at the beginning of this section, with a focus on the challenges posed by the accumulation of waste in different locations, which has a detrimental effect on the environment and the living conditions of locals. There is a thorough discussion of Nigeria's waste management legislative framework, which includes the Federal Republic of Nigeria's Constitution, the NESREA Act, the National Environmental (Sanitation and Wastes Control) Regulations, and the National Policy on the Environment. Nevertheless, there are barriers to the efficient implementation of these legal systems. This section outlines waste management in Nigeria, reviews the current legal structures, and highlights the challenges that impede effective waste management in the nation.

3.1 Legal and Institutional Framework for Solid Waste Management

One major source of environmental risks is municipal trash. Nigeria's environmental protection regulatory framework has been given particular attention, as will be shown below. It is still unclear, though, if Nigeria's regulatory structure can handle the difficulties brought on by the country's rising trash production rate. The management

and disposal of trash are governed by a large number of laws and organisations in Nigeria. The Federal Ministry of Environment, State Environmental Ministries, the Ministry of Water Resources, the Lagos State Waste Management Authority (LSWMA) and other state waste management authorities, state environmental protection organisations like the Lagos State Environmental Protection Agency (LASEPA), and state waste disposal boards like the Lagos State Waste Disposal Board (LSWDB) are among the agencies. The National Environmental Standards Regulations and Enforcement Agency (NESREA) is one of them. The different Acts and Regulations on wastes management on wastes in Nigeria include:

3.1.1 The 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (CFRN)²⁷

Nigeria's supreme law, the CFRN 1999, serves as the constitutional basis for waste management and environmental preservation. It enables the government to create institutions for sustainable development and environmental management as well as to pass laws.²⁸ The CFRN states that the government must protect and improve the environment and safeguard Nigeria's water, air, and land.²⁹ This provision is, however, contained in Chapter II of the CFRN, which establishes the fundamental objectives and directive principles of state policy, which are, sadly, non-justiciable.³⁰ In *Attorney-General, Ondo State v. Attorney General of the Federation*³¹, as was the case with regard to section 15(5) of the 1999 Constitution as amended, the Supreme Court ruled, among other things, that courts cannot enforce any of the provisions of Chapter II of the constitution until the National Assembly has passed explicit legislation for their implementation. The Supreme Court holds that the goals and tenets that form the constitutional policy of governance are merely statements that the legal system cannot enforce, but if state organs behaved in obvious disdain, it would be viewed as a failure of duty and obligation. The court went on to assert that laws may make the Directive Principles or at least some of them justiciable.

3.1.2 The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA)³²

The National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) Act of 2007 made NESREA Nigeria's main regulatory agency in charge of upholding waste management and other environmental standards. The power to oversee, control, and

²⁷Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended) Cap. C23 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004

²⁸ CFRN, S.1

²⁹ Ibid. S.20

³⁰ Ibid. S.6(6)(c)

³¹ *Ondo State & Ors v Attorney-General of the Federation & Ors* [2002] 9 NWLR (Pt. 772) 222.

³² National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (Establishment) Act 2007 s.1. The Act was amended in 2008. See The NESREA (establishment) Act 2008 (as amended) Cap. N164 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria.

enforce adherence to environmental regulations and standards, including waste management, rests with NESREA.³³

This is Nigeria's main legislation regarding environmental protection at present. The Act was amended in 2008. The Act created the National Environmental Standards Regulatory and Enforcement Agency (NESREA) to take over the functions of the Federal Environmental Protection Agency (FEPA). NESREA is now the key agency responsible for ensuring adherence to environmental laws, both at the national and international levels, focused on pollution prevention and control, as well as environmental sanitation through monitoring and regulatory actions. It also has the authority to establish regulations concerning air and water quality, effluent standards, control of harmful substances, and other types of environmental pollution and sanitation.³⁴

NESREA plays a vital role in waste management by monitoring and regulating activities that have an impact on the environment, including waste disposal and management practices. One of the key functions of NESREA is to develop and enforce guidelines for waste collection, transportation, treatment, and disposal. These guidelines are aimed at ensuring proper waste management practices and minimizing environmental pollution. The agency sets standards and regulations for waste generators, outlining their responsibilities in waste management processes. It also establishes penalties for non-compliance, providing a legal framework for waste management practices in Nigeria.³⁵ However, the agency is barred from exercising its authority in the oil and gas industry.³⁶

In 2018, a notable amendment was made to the NESREA Act. This change introduced important enhancements to the agency's responsibilities and roles. The amendment increased NESREA's powers by allowing it to regulate and enforce environmental standards in previously excluded sectors, like the oil and gas industry. This was a positive step forward, enabling NESREA to utilize its authority and take a more extensive approach in tackling environmental issues, including waste management, across all economic sectors.

The amendment also established tougher penalties and sanctions for breaches of environmental laws, focusing on improving adherence to environmental regulations. It highlighted the necessity of conducting environmental impact assessments for initiatives and activities that could have considerable environmental effects. Additionally, the amendment reinforced the regulations concerning waste management, pollution prevention, and environmental monitoring, empowering NESREA to take more efficient

³³Ibid

³⁴ Ibid. ss.7&8

³⁵ National Environmental (Sanitation and Wastes Control) Regulations, 2009.

³⁶ Ibid. s.7 (g - l); D. Olawuyi 'The Principles of Nigerian Environmental Law' (2013) *Business Perspectives*,34.

measures in promoting environmental sustainability. The changes introduced by the 2018 Act represent a pledge to enhance environmental governance and bolster NESREA's ability to tackle environmental issues, particularly in waste management. By broadening NESREA's regulatory powers and strengthening its enforcement capabilities, the amendment seeks to foster improved environmental practices, safeguard ecosystems, and reduce the harmful effects of pollution and poor waste management practices in Nigeria.

However, NESREA faces several challenges that hinder its effectiveness in waste management. One significant challenge is the lack of a comprehensive national database on environmental quality. The absence of such a database makes it difficult for environmental agencies, including NESREA, to monitor and assess the progress of waste management initiatives in Nigeria. This lack of real-time environmental data hampers the ability to make informed decisions and track the effectiveness of waste management strategies.³⁷

Another challenge is the shortage of staff within NESREA and other environmental agencies. The limited number of personnel undermines their capacity to enforce environmental standards and regulations effectively. Insufficient technical expertise and manpower within the agency impede its ability to carry out its responsibilities and ensure compliance with waste management laws.³⁸ Additionally, the presence of multiple agencies with overlapping mandates poses a challenge to waste management in Nigeria. Different agencies may have their own standards and regulations, leading to inconsistencies in enforcement and compliance. This multiplicity of agencies can create confusion and hinder the harmonization of waste management practices across the country.

In spite of these challenges, NESREA remains a crucial institutional framework for waste management in Nigeria. Efforts to address the challenges and strengthen NESREA's capacity, such as improving data collection systems, increasing staffing levels, and enhancing coordination among relevant agencies, are essential for effective waste management and environmental protection in the country.

3.1.3 National Environmental (Sanitation and Wastes Control) Regulations, 2009³⁹

The National Environmental Regulations on Sanitation and Waste Control from 2009 outlines specific measures for the control, management, and disposal of waste throughout Nigeria. It defines the duties of waste producers as well as the processes for collection,

³⁷ A. Adewole, 'Waste Management in Nigeria: Challenges and Potential Solutions' (2018) 6(5) *International Journal of Environmental Protection and Policy*, 106-111.

³⁸ *Ibid* (n 46)

³⁹ Statutory Instrument No.28 2009

transportation, treatment, and disposal. The regulations set forth penalties for those who do not comply and create a legal basis for practices in waste management.⁴⁰ The regulations are segmented into seven sections, with each section containing eighteen schedules, and they apply widely to issues related to environmental sanitation, especially concerning food, market, and industrial waste management and hygiene, alongside the different types of waste produced, specifically focusing on community, end-of-life, hazardous, healthcare, industrial, radioactive, leaf, yard, solid, and packaging waste.⁴¹

The Polluter-Pays Principle,⁴² which is founded on the straightforward idea that everyone should be accountable for cleaning up their waste, citizens' obligations, extended producer responsibility, general cleanliness, and the responsibilities of property owners and occupants are all covered in the various sections on environmental sanitation. According to the principle, the polluter who damages the environment is responsible for paying for repairs and victim compensation.⁴³ Among other things, the laws contain measures for regulating solid waste, effluent discharge, and hazardous and medical wastes.⁴⁴ Additionally, the rules stipulate that trash and garbage must be disposed of in the appropriate litter receptacles and nowhere else. No property's owners, operators, inhabitants, or those in charge of administering or overseeing it allow garbage to be released into the environment.⁴⁵ It is illegal for anyone, even car owners, to leave trash on Nigerian roads, highways, or public areas.⁴⁶

More importantly, the agency (NESREA) is responsible for ensuring the implementation of the 2005 National Environmental Sanitation Policy and Guidelines at all levels of government⁴⁷, as well as encouraging strategic cooperation and collaboration among all levels of government.⁴⁸ The regulations also recognize the importance of penalizing offenders⁴⁹ and harmonizing intervention programs.⁵⁰

⁴⁰ Ibid (n 47).

⁴¹ M.T Ladan, 'Review of NESREA Act 2007 And Regulations 2009-2011: A New Dawn in Environmental Compliance and Enforcement in Nigeria' (2012) 8(1) *Law, Environment and Development Journal*, 130.

⁴² Ibid (n 47) Regulations 3-22.

⁴³ Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment in the Northeast Atlantic (OSPAR Convention) art.2(2)(b); D. Olawuyi 'The Principles of Nigerian Environmental Law' (2013) *Business Perspectives*,34.

⁴⁴ Ibid (n 47) Regulations 23-62

⁴⁵ Ibid (n 47) Regulation 3

⁴⁶ National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Act, 2007. S. 5.

⁴⁷ Ibid (n 47) Regulation 63

⁴⁸ Ibid (n 47) Regulations 63-65

⁴⁹ Ibid (n 47) Regulations 66-104

⁵⁰ Ibid (n 47) Regulation 105

3.1.4 Environmental Impact Assessment Act of 1992⁵¹

Potential environmental effects of development projects, including waste management initiatives, must be evaluated and controlled in accordance with the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) Act of 1992. The EIA procedure guarantees that waste management projects are assessed for their effects on the environment, society, and economy prior to approval.⁵² According to this Act, development projects that could have an impact on the environment must first undergo an environmental impact assessment. It prohibits starting initiatives that could have a major negative impact on the environment without first taking those impacts into account.⁵³ If a project is anticipated to have unjustified, irreversible, and substantial negative environmental effects, it will not be allowed.⁵⁴

3.1.5 The National Policy on the Environment⁵⁵

The Nigerian National Policy on the Environment serves as a guiding document for managing the environment and promoting sustainable development. It lays out a framework for waste management practices, highlighting the importance of waste reduction, recycling, and responsible disposal methods that are environmentally friendly.⁵⁶ This document acts as Nigeria's roadmap for environmental sustainability. It demonstrates Nigeria's dedication to sustainable development grounded in effective environmental management. Its goals include, among other things, fostering an environment that supports health and well-being.⁵⁷ Strategies to accomplish these aims consist of establishing appropriate environmental standards, monitoring and assessing environmental changes, releasing environmental data, conducting prior environmental impact assessments for proposed activities, and implementing environmentally friendly technologies in the management of natural resources, among other initiatives.

3.1.6 National Environmental (Base Metals, Iron, and Steel Manufacturing/Recycling Industries Sector) Regulations 2011⁵⁸

The National Environmental Regulations of 2011 concerning the base metals, iron, and steel manufacturing/recycling sectors tackle waste management concerns in these industries. These rules set forth criteria and directions for the management and disposal

⁵¹ Cap. E12 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria.

⁵² Environmental Impact Assessment Act, 1992

⁵³ Ibid s.2

⁵⁴ Ibid s.30

⁵⁵ National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA). 'The National Policy on the Environment Regulations' (September 2017) < <http://www.nesrea.gov.ng/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/National-Policyon-Environment.pdf>> accessed 17 February 2025

⁵⁶ Federal Government of Nigeria. (2016). 'National Policy on the Environment. Abuja: Federal Ministry of Environment'.

⁵⁷ Ibid

⁵⁸ Cap. N164 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria

of waste within these sectors.⁵⁹ This regulation aims to prevent and reduce pollution in the Nigerian environment caused by the sector's operations and ancillary activities.⁶⁰ New facilities, corporations, and organizations in the sector are expected to use efficient "cleaner production technologies" to reduce pollution as much as possible.⁶¹ Every facility, corporation, or organization must follow the 5Rs (Reduce, Repair, Reuse, Recycle, and Recover) in managing scraps generated during production.⁶²

3.1.7 The Harmful Wastes (Special Criminal Provisions and Others) Act 1988⁶³

For the most part, this Act is a criminal law. Any of the actions or inactions listed in Section 12 of the Act constitutes the offences. In reaction to the Koko dumping disaster, Nigeria passed its first law, criminalizing the unlawful disposal of hazardous waste on Nigerian soil or in Nigerian waterways. To transport, drop, dump, import, sell, offer for sale, negotiate, or buy any hazardous material on Nigerian territory, inland waterways, contiguous zones, exclusive economic zones, or territorial waters is illegal.⁶⁴

4. CHALLENGES AND GAPS IN THE LEGAL AND INSTITUTIONAL FRAMEWORK

Despite the presence of a legal framework, Nigeria faces several challenges and gaps in municipal waste management. This subsection discusses the key challenges, such as inadequate funding, limited infrastructure, poor public awareness, and capacity constraints. It also examines the gaps within the existing legal framework, such as the need for more precise definitions, updated regulations, and enhanced enforcement provisions. Understanding these challenges and gaps is crucial for devising strategies to strengthen the legal framework and improve waste management practices. Some of the challenges include;

1. **Overpopulation and Insufficient Funding:** Nigerian waste management requires a significant financial investment due to its capital-intensive nature. Regrettably, despite the fact that state governments make significant investments in trash management, the available funds are not enough to keep up with the rate of garbage generation. This suggests that more attention should be paid to

⁵⁹ National Environmental (Base Metals, Iron and Steel Manufacturing / Recycling Industries Sector) Regulations, 2011.

⁶⁰ Ibid. Regulation 1

⁶¹ Ibid. Regulation 3(2)

⁶² V. Aigbokhaevbo, 'Environmental abuses in Nigeria: Sectoral implications for reproductive health care' (2018) *Maiden edition NIALS Journal of Health Law and Policy*, 187.

⁶³ Cap. H1 Laws of the Federation of Nigeria.

⁶⁴ Harmful Waste (Special Criminal Provision, and others) Act. Section 1(2)(a).

minimizing the amount of waste produced rather than managing it once it has been produced.⁶⁵

2. Lack of qualified or experienced waste managers: More qualified trash managers are required for the Lagos State waste management system. Even worse, things are not much better in the private waste management industry, where the majority of waste management companies use seasoned professionals who have no understanding of effective trash management.⁶⁶
3. Lack of Effective Control and Monitoring of Waste Disposal Authorities: Due to the lack of competition in this sector, operational authorities are not held to high standards.⁶⁷

Some of the identified gaps include;

1. Outdated Regulations: The existing legal framework may suffer from outdated regulations such as state environmental regulations that do not adequately address emerging waste management challenges. Rapid urbanization and technological advancements require laws responsive to evolving waste management practices, such as recycling and e-waste management. The absence of updated regulations can create gaps in addressing these current waste management issues.⁶⁸
2. Inadequate Enforcement Provisions: Effective enforcement mechanisms are essential for ensuring compliance with waste management regulations. However, the current legal framework NESREA have gaps in terms of enforcement provisions, including weak penalties, limited inspection and monitoring capacities, and insufficient coordination among regulatory agencies. These gaps undermine the enforcement of waste management regulations and contribute to non-compliant practices.⁶⁹

Addressing these gaps requires specific measures to strengthen the legal framework for waste management in Nigeria. Recommendations to bridge these gaps include:

1. Reviewing and updating the existing waste management regulations to incorporate more precise definitions and provisions that address emerging waste management challenges.

⁶⁵ L. Nwokike, (2020). 'Lagos waste management authority law and national environmental standards and regulations enforcement agency (establishment) Act: A comparative Appraisal' (2020) 26(1) *African Journal of Law and Human Rights* 121.

⁶⁶ Ibid

⁶⁷ Ibid

⁶⁸ C. Johnson, *East Asia's Arms Races* (Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 1948) 18.

⁶⁹ M. Adeel, 'Challenges in Waste Management in Developing Countries.' (1 July 2017) 35(10) *Waste Management & Research* 1063-1074. doi: 10.1016/j.wasman.2017.07.001.

2. Strengthening enforcement provisions by imposing stricter penalties for non-compliance, enhancing inspection and monitoring capacities, and promoting coordination among regulatory agencies.
3. Encouraging multi-stakeholder collaboration and coordination through establishing platforms for dialogue and cooperation among government agencies, waste management operators, and community representatives.
4. Conducting regular reviews and assessments of the legal framework to ensure its relevance and effectiveness in addressing evolving waste management practices.

By addressing these gaps in the legal framework, can enhance its waste management practices, promote sustainable waste management systems, and protect public health and the environment.

5. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In summary, the handling of solid waste in Nigeria has highlighted numerous challenges and shortcomings that impede efficient waste management practices. This research underscored the importance of thorough reforms and focused measures to tackle these problems. There is a distinct necessity for restructuring or implementing new systems within the current legal and institutional frameworks. This study indicates that, despite having operational structures, ineffective waste management continues to be an issue. By looking to developed nations for inspiration, Nigeria can create systems that focus on developing infrastructure, establishing waste sorting and treatment facilities, and implementing proper disposal methods. This approach could help reconcile the discrepancies between the existing frameworks and the actual waste management practices.

Secondly, engaging citizens and promoting public participation are essential components for effective waste management. The study underscores the significance of behavioral change initiatives, media outreach, and incentives to inspire the Nigerian population to actively engage in waste reduction, source separation, and recycling efforts. By cultivating a sense of accountability and increasing awareness about the environmental consequences of waste, Nigeria can motivate its citizens to adopt sustainable waste management habits.

Thirdly, financial viability is crucial for the successful operation of waste management systems. Lack of adequate funding adversely affects various areas, including staffing, training, and obtaining essential equipment. To tackle this issue, Nigeria should investigate creative funding solutions such as taxes, long-term planning, and fee structures. Sufficient financial resources will empower the legal and institutional frameworks to carry out their duties and enhance waste containment and recovery.

Furthermore, the study emphasizes the significance of minimizing waste and enhancing recycling as essential measures to ease the pressure on waste management systems. By employing improved management strategies and advocating for recycling initiatives, Nigeria has the potential to considerably lower waste output and enhance resource efficiency. In addition, initiatives should focus on curbing the production of plastic products and promoting eco-friendly alternatives to reduce the environmental risks tied to plastic waste. In summary, the comparative evaluation highlights the necessity of a comprehensive approach that integrates legal and institutional reforms, public participation, financial viability, waste minimization, and recycling efforts. By tackling these issues and executing the proposed strategies, Lagos and Anambra States, Nigeria, can improve their waste management approaches, lessen environmental pollution, and progress towards a more sustainable future.

5.1 Recommendations

On the strength of the discussion above, the following additional recommendations are proposed to improve the legal framework and waste management practices in Nigeria:

1. **Enhancing Supportive Measures and Infrastructure:** The results emphasize the necessity of bolstering supportive measures in conjunction with legal and institutional frameworks for efficient waste management. To tackle the ongoing challenge of inadequate waste management, Nigeria ought to think about reorganizing or implementing new systems inspired by the practices of developed nations.⁷⁰ These systems should prioritize investment in infrastructure for waste sorting, treatment, landfills, bins, transfer stations, trucks, and dumpsters.⁷¹ By upgrading existing infrastructure and providing necessary facilities, Nigeria can create a solid foundation for improved waste management practices.
2. **Citizen Engagement and Public Participation:** In addition to legal and institutional frameworks, citizen engagement and public participation are crucial aspects of effective waste management.⁷² The study underscores the importance of enhancing citizen involvement by utilizing behavioral change strategies supported by the media. By increasing awareness regarding waste management practices and their effects on the environment, the public can be inspired to engage in waste reduction, source separation, and reuse efforts. Launching awareness campaigns

⁷⁰ R. Srivastav 'Waste Management: Developed and Developing Countries' (November 2016) 5(3) *International Journal of Science and Research* 202-203.

⁷¹ The World Bank, 'Solid Waste Management' <<https://www.worldbank.org/en/topic/urbandevelopment/brief/solidwaste-management>> Accessed 14 March 2025

⁷² Ibid

and providing incentives can additionally promote public involvement and cultivate a culture of responsible waste management.

3. **Financial Stability and Resource Allocation:** A significant obstacle highlighted in waste management systems is the inadequacy of funding. Limited financial resources impede multiple facets of waste management, such as employee compensation, the ability to hire qualified personnel, and the procurement of essential tools and equipment. To tackle this issue, Nigeria needs to emphasize financial stability in waste management systems. This can be accomplished by investigating various funding strategies, including tax utilization, long-term planning, and fee structures.⁷³ By ensuring adequate financial resources, the legal frameworks can realistically fulfill their responsibilities and improve waste containment and recovery.
4. **Waste Minimization and Recycling:** The findings of the research suggest that Nigeria is confronted with a major issue stemming from the vast quantity of waste produced by its citizens. To ease the pressure on legal and institutional frameworks, there needs to be a collective initiative aimed at decreasing the volume of waste that is discarded. In this context, recycling stands out as an essential solution. Drawing inspiration from developed countries like Germany⁷⁴, advanced waste management techniques, such as Enhanced Resolution and Mobile sorting, should be adopted. These techniques increase the likelihood of waste reuse and recycling. By implementing effective recycling initiatives, Nigeria can significantly improve its waste management practices and reduce reliance on landfills. It is essential to create awareness among the Nigerian populace about the benefits of recycling and encourage active participation in recycling programs.⁷⁵
5. **Decreasing Plastic Material Production:** A considerable amount of municipal solid waste in Nigeria consists of plastic materials, which are poorly recycled, resulting in their buildup in landfills, dumping sites, and drainage systems.⁷⁶ To tackle this challenge, the study suggests reducing the production of plastic materials. Nigeria should implement strategies to encourage reuse and a more efficient utilization of existing resources. This could be accomplished by enacting policies and regulations that discourage overconsumption of plastic products and promote the use of sustainable alternatives. By lowering plastic production, Nigeria can reduce

⁷³ Ibid

⁷⁴ R. Srivastav 'Waste Management: Developed and Developing Countries' (November 2016) 5(3) *International Journal of Science and Research* 202-203.

⁷⁵ Ibid

⁷⁶ O. Kehinde, O.J Ramonu, K.O Babaremu and L.D Justin, 'Plastic wastes: environmental hazard and instrument for wealth creation in Nigeria' (2020) 6(10) *Helion*, 05131.

waste generation and disposal, easing the pressure on waste management systems and lessening the environmental risks linked to plastic waste.

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